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Integrated Agricultural Solid Waste-To-Energy (ASWtE) Policy Framework for Sustainable Rural Development in Daet, Camarines Norte

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Abstract.

This study was conducted to assess the generation and energy potential of agricultural solid wastes and determine the problem and challenges and the readiness of LGU Daet in terms of Agricultural Solid Waste-to-Energy as well as to develop an integrated policy framework and local ordinance for the establishment of a sustainable Agricultural Solid Waste-to-Energy system in the municipality. Specifically, it aimed to address the following queries: (1) what particular agricultural solid wastes are generated in Daet, Camarines Norte, in terms of classification and annual volume: (1.1) plant and crop wastes; (1.2) animal refuse; and (1.3) agro-industrial residues? (2) what is the potential energy capacity of these agricultural residues as a sustainable feedstock for the waste-to-energy systems relative to: (2.1) calorific or heating value; and (2.2) biogas yields? (3) what are the practices pertaining to agricultural solid waste-to-energy technologies implemented in Daet, Camarines Norte? (4) what are the problems associated with the adoption of agricultural solid waste-to-energy management and practices in Daet, Camarines Norte? (5) what policy framework can be developed to assure that the agricultural solid waste-to-energy systems are integrated into Daet's local governance from the point of view of legislation, implementation, and monitoring strategies?

Actual study was conducted in the Municipality of Daet, Camarines Norte, involving 350 farmer-respondents selected as the primary sources of quantitative data and the key informant interviews were also conducted with the 15 National Government (NGA) and Local Government Unit (LGU) officials, cooperative leaders, agro-industrial operators and agricultural experts and other relevant stakeholders to gather qualitative insights on policy gaps, implementation challenges, and institutional readiness and to strengthen the quantitative findings.

A mixed-method descriptive research design was employed in this study. Quantitative data were collected through structured survey questionnaires administered to farmers to determine waste generation practices and volumes and assessed the existing waste utilization and disposal as well as to assess the policy implementation, its challenges and barriers as well as the readiness

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of the LGU to implement agricultural solid waste-to-energy system, while qualitative data were obtained through the key informant interviews (KII) to support and strengthen the insight gathered and generated thereon.

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistical tools such as frequency counts, percentages, and weighted means for the agricultural solid wastes such as plants and crops wastes, animal refuse and agro-industrial residues. For the determination of its energy conversion computations were aided by the secondary data available to estimate calorific values and the biogas potential. This quantitative data was also cross validated using the key informant interview and is analyze utilizing the Braun and Clarke (2006) six-phase framework for thematic analysis and was operationalized through the use of Lumivero. (2025). NVivo (Version 15).

The findings revealed that the Municipality of Daet generates a substantial volume of agricultural solid wastes of around 19,521,987 per/year, primarily composed of 12,780,810.88 kg/year of plant and crop wastes, 984,916.00 kg/year of animal refuse, and 5,756,260.07 kg/year of agro-industrial by-products and residues, with plant and crop wastes contributing the largest share of biomass availability. That generated all of the waste management practices remain largely traditional and disposal-oriented, including open dumping, uncontrolled decomposition, and occasional burning, contributing to environmental degradation and greenhouse gas emissions and the worst - flooding and flash floods. Respondents demonstrated limited awareness and practice of Waste-to-Energy technologies, indicating that ASWtE systems are not yet widely implemented or institutionalized. Computed results further showed that agricultural solid wastes have significant energy potential of around 226.9 million MJ/year or its corresponding equivalent electricity of 63.04 million kWh/year or in aggregate of 135.9 million MJ/year for plant and crops wastes with 37.75 million kWh/year, 12.78 million MJ/year for animal refuse with 3.55 million kWh/year and 78.25 million MJ/year for agro-industrial residues with 21.74 million kWh/year. This data is deemed to be capable of generating substantial thermal energy and millions of kilowatt-hours of electricity annually, sufficient to power several thousand households depending on system efficiency such as 15,760 household for 25 % power conversion efficiency and 25,216 household for the 40% efficiency solely for the Total Calorific Value derived from agricultural solid wastes. On the Total Potential Biogas yield, with its 19.5 million kilograms produced per year has a potential biogas yield of around 6.71 million cu.m. /year and its potential energy is 147.68 million MJ/year and around 18.36 million kWh/year. It has an aggregate of 82.94 million MJ/year for plant and crop wastes with 8.07 million kWh/year, 6.99 million MJ/year with 0.68 million kWh/year, and 98.67 million MJ/year with 9.60 million kWh/year. This can possible generate substantial thermal energy that can be able to power around 1,739 households for the 25% power conversion efficiency and around 2,782 households for the 40% power conversion efficiency. Key informant interviews also revealed existing policy gaps, institutional limitations, and inadequate infrastructure hindering implementation, although stakeholders expressed strong support for ASWtE development due to its perceived environmental, economic, and energy benefits. The proposed Integrated Policy Framework and draft local ordinance were identified as necessary mechanisms to address these gaps and support system implementation.

Based on the findings, an Integrated Policy Framework for ASWtE and a proposed local ordinance were developed to provide a structured governance system for sustainable waste-to-energy implementation. The study concludes that agricultural solid wastes in Daet represent a viable renewable energy resource, and that the establishment of a policy-supported ASWtE system can significantly contribute to environmental protection, energy generation, and rural development in the municipality.

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn. Agricultural solid wastes in the Municipality of Daet represent a viable and significantly underutilized resource that can be effectively converted into renewable energy through appropriate Waste-to-Energy (WtE) technologies such as anaerobic digestion and biomass conversion systems. This confirms

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the technical potential of agricultural residues as an alternative and sustainable energy source. The current waste management system in the municipality remains largely disposal-oriented, indicating that it is not yet sufficiently developed to support sustainable resource recovery. Existing practices are primarily focused on waste disposal rather than circular economy approaches such as energy recovery, material reuse, and integrated biomass utilization. There exists a significant gap in awareness, technical capacity, infrastructure, and policy support necessary for the full implementation of Agricultural Solid Waste-to-Energy (ASWtE) systems in the locality. These gaps limit the ability of the municipality to maximize the environmental and economic value of agricultural wastes. The estimated energy potential derived from agricultural solid wastes demonstrates that ASWtE systems can contribute meaningfully to local energy generation. This includes the potential to supply electricity for household consumption and support community-level energy needs, thereby enhancing local energy security and sustainability. The integration of quantitative survey results and qualitative key informant interview data confirms that while technical and institutional challenges persist, there is strong stakeholder acceptance and a favorable level of institutional readiness for the adoption of ASWtE systems, provided that appropriate policies, infrastructure, and governance mechanisms are established.

Finally, the proposed Integrated Policy Framework and draft local ordinance are essential governance instruments that can address existing gaps and institutionalize a structured, sustainable, and locally managed ASWtE system in the Municipality of Daet, Camarines Norte. These policy tools are critical in ensuring long-term implementation, coordination, and sustainability of agricultural waste-to-energy initiatives.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proposed such as: (1) The Municipal Government of Daet is encouraged to institutionalize the proposed Integrated Agricultural Solid Waste-to-Energy (ASWtE) Policy Framework to guide sustainable waste management and renewable energy development. (2) The Sangguniang Bayan should prioritize the enactment of the proposed ordinance to provide the legal and institutional basis for ASWtE implementation.

(3) The LGU, in partnership with relevant agencies and private sector stakeholders, should develop appropriate Waste-to-Energy infrastructure such as biogas digesters, biomass systems, and material recovery facilities. (4) Capacity-building and awareness programs should be strengthened to enhance stakeholder knowledge and participation in proper waste segregation and biomass utilization. (5) A multi-sectoral coordination mechanism should be established to ensure effective planning, implementation, and monitoring of ASWtE initiatives. (6) Appropriate financing schemes such as Public-Private Partnerships (PPP), grants, and environmental funds should be explored to support infrastructure development and long-term sustainability. (7) Finally, pilot implementation and further feasibility studies are recommended to validate and refine the proposed framework for wider application.

Keywords: *Agricultural Solid Waste-to-Energy (ASWtE), Waste-to-Energy System, Circular Economy, Integrated Policy Formulation, Biomass Energy*